

Comparative evaluation of efficacy of acupressure and temporal tapping technique versus standard distraction method in preventing gag reflex during impression making

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Abstract— Background: Exaggerated gag reflex poses a significant challenge in dental impression making, affecting patient comfort and treatment quality. Non-pharmacological techniques are preferred alternatives to medication for gag control.

Aim: To compare the effectiveness of acupressure, temporal tapping, and standard distraction methods in managing gag reflex during maxillary impressions.

Methods: Thirty patients with moderate to severe gag reflex [Gag Severity Index (GSI) ≥ 2] were randomized into three groups: standard distraction, temporal tapping, and acupressure at Neiguan (P6). Each group underwent two sequential maxillary impressions, without and with the intervention. Gag reflex severity was measured by the Gag Prevention Index (GPI) at 0, 30, 60, and 120 seconds after tray insertion. Patient comfort was assessed by a 5-point patient reported scale.

Results: Acupressure showed the lowest mean GPI scores (0.8 ± 0.3 to 0.9 ± 0.3) at all timepoints, significantly better than temporal tapping (1.1 ± 0.3 to 1.7 ± 0.6) and standard distraction (3.3 ± 0.6 to 3.8 ± 0.6) ($p < 0.01$). Temporal tapping was superior to standard distraction ($p < 0.05$). Patient comfort scores were highest in the acupressure group (4.6 ± 0.4), followed by temporal tapping (3.2 ± 0.6), with standard distraction lowest (1.4 ± 0.5) ($p < 0.05$).

Conclusion: Acupressure at Neiguan (P6) effectively and consistently reduces gag reflex severity and enhances patient comfort compared to temporal tapping and standard distraction methods. Combining standard distraction method with sensory-based techniques may further optimize gag control in clinical dental practice. Larger trials incorporating adjunctive modalities are warranted.

Keywords— *Gag reflex, Acupressure, Temporal tapping, Standard distraction technique*

I. INTRODUCTION

The gag reflex is a normal, protective physiological mechanism that serves as a defense against the ingestion or aspiration of potentially harmful foreign bodies. It is mediated by afferent stimulation of the glossopharyngeal and trigeminal nerves, followed by an efferent response via the vagus nerve, which causes spasmodic contractions of the oropharyngeal musculature [1]. While necessary for airway protection, an exaggerated gag reflex frequently presents a significant clinical challenge in dentistry, especially during procedures such as impression making, intraoral radiography, and prosthodontic rehabilitation. Its presence can compromise treatment quality, patient comfort, and the efficiency of dental care delivery [2,3].

Patients with gag reflex are generally classified into two groups: somatogenic gaggers, in whom mechanical stimulation such as contact with dental instruments induces gagging, and psychogenic gaggers, where the response arises primarily from anxiety, fear, or psychological anticipation of the procedure [4]. Stimuli capable of triggering gagging may include not only tactile factors but also gustatory, olfactory, visual, acoustic, and psychogenic cues [5]. The severity and threshold of this reflex vary considerably by individual, and studies suggest associations with parameters such as gender, dental anxiety, and past negative dental experiences [6].

Management of the exaggerated gag reflex has traditionally involved both pharmacological and non-pharmacological approaches. Pharmacological methods include the use of topical anaesthetics, sedatives, antihistamines, or centrally acting depressants, though these may carry adverse effects or require advanced monitoring [7]. Consequently, non-pharmacological approaches are often preferred in general dental practice. These include simple behavioural distraction, desensitization strategies, and adjunctive methods such as salt application on the tongue, prosthetic training devices, acupuncture, transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS), and laser stimulation [8,9].

Among distraction-based methods, the temporal tapping technique is a non-invasive sensory modulation method first described by Goodheart. It involves rhythmic tapping along the temporal-sphenoidal line in front of the ear, providing multisensory input that diverts attention and reduces reflexogenic oropharyngeal sensitivity [10]. Similarly, acupressure, which is based on traditional Chinese medicine, requires applying firm pressure to specific acupoints in order to regulate physiological responses. In dentistry, acupressure applied at points such as Neiguan (P6, located on the wrist), Hegu (LI4, between thumb and index finger), or Chengjiang (CV24, below the lower lip) has shown promise in alleviating nausea, anxiety, and gagging by modulating neural input and reducing hyper-responsivity [11,12]. Its simplicity, safety, and suitability for use in routine practice make it an attractive adjunctive method for gag control, particularly in psychologically mediated gaggers.

Despite their clinical applicability, robust comparative evidence regarding the efficacy of acupressure and temporal tapping for gag reflex control in dental impression making remains sparse. Much of the literature consists of anecdotal reports or isolated small-scale studies, with limited standardized assessment of gag severity or reproducibility of outcomes [13,14]. In contrast, conventional distraction methods such as standard distraction techniques are widely practiced but may be insufficient in patients with severe gagging tendencies [15].

Given these gaps, evaluating the relative effectiveness of alternative non-pharmacological methods is clinically relevant. This study aims to assess and compare the impact of acupressure and temporal tapping techniques against standard distraction technique during dental impression making. By systematically comparing these approaches using a validated subjective five-point patient reported scale, the present study seeks to provide evidence-based insights that will aid clinicians in tailoring gag control strategies to individual patient needs, improve patient comfort, reduce procedural interruptions, and enhance overall treatment outcomes.

II. METHODOLOGY

This randomized comparative clinical study was conducted in the Department of Prosthodontics, Rajarajeswari Dental college and hospital, Bangalore, after obtaining approval from the Institutional Ethics Committee (RRDCH/IEC/2024/038). Written informed consent was obtained from all participants before enrolment. The study aimed to evaluate and compare the efficacy of acupressure and temporal tapping techniques with the standard distraction technique in preventing gag reflex during impression making.

The study included 30 patients with an exaggerated gag reflex. The sample size was calculated with an α error of 5% and β error of 20%, resulting in an 80% power level. Gag intensity was assessed using the Gag Severity Index (GSI) (Table I) and Gag Prevention Index (GPI) (Table II), both validated tools developed by Dickinson and Fiske [16]. Eligibility criteria included patients aged 18–60 years with a GSI score of 2 or higher on the Dickinson and Fiske index. Patients with systemic illnesses such as vertigo or seizure disorders, those under sedatives or anxiolytics, or with previous experience of acupuncture or acupressure therapy were excluded. Eligible participants were randomly allocated into three study groups, with ten patients per group, using the odd–even randomization method. Group I patients received the standard distraction technique (control), Group II received the temporal tapping technique (TTT), and Group III received acupressure intervention. Due to the nature of the procedures, blinding of both patients and investigators was not feasible, which is typical of studies involving behavioural and manual interventions.

To standardize procedures and minimize operator bias, all impressions were made in irreversible hydrocolloid (alginate) by a single trained investigator. Tray selection and material manipulation were standardized, and patient gag scores were recorded by a single trained investigator. Additionally, verbal distraction in the form of light conversation was provided to all patients, regardless of the group, so that this variable was consistent across interventions.

TABLE I
GAG SEVERITY INDEX (GSI)¹⁶

Grade	Gag severity index (GSI)
I	Very mild, occasional and controlled by the patient
II	Mild, and control is required by the patient with reassurance from the dental team
III	Moderate, consistent and limits treatment options
IV	Severe and treatment is impossible
V	Very severe; affecting patient behavior and dental attendance and making treatment impossible.

TABLE II
GAG PREVENTION INDEX (GPI)¹⁶

Grade	Gag prevention index (GPI)
I	Obtunded Gag Reflex (GR) ; proposed treatment successful.
II	Partially controlled GR; treatment possible but occasional gagging.
III	Partially controlled GR but frequent gagging; treatment was part completed.
IV	Inadequately controlled GR; gagging occurred regularly; treatment unable to be completed.
V	GR severe; no treatment possible.

In this study, each patient underwent two sequential maxillary impressions with a 10-minute washout period between them to minimize carryover effects, as gag reflexes mechanically induced during impression making typically subside within a few minutes. In Group I (Control), the first impression was made without intervention and after a 10 minute washout period, a second impression was made using the standard distraction method (Figure 1). In Group II (Temporal Tapping Technique), a maxillary impression was first recorded without intervention, and after the 10 mins washout period, a second impression was made following the application of the temporal tapping technique (Figure 2). This entailed rhythmic tapping along the temporal–sphenoidal line, starting anterior to the ear and moving forward and upward, for approximately 45–60 seconds before tray insertion.

In Group III, a maxillary impression was first made without intervention and a second impression was made after 10minute washout period following the acupressure stimulation (Figure 3). The Neiguan (P6) point, located on the anterior surface of the wrist roughly three finger breadths proximal to the wrist crease, was selected for stimulation. Firm thumb pressure was applied at this site for approximately two minutes, gradually increased until the patient reported a sensation of mild soreness or tightness.

Outcome assessment included evaluation of gag reflex using the Gag Prevention Index (GPI), with scores recorded at 0 seconds, 30 seconds, 1 minute, and 2 minutes after tray placement. Baseline gagging response had already been screened using the GSI. In addition, after the second impression, patients were asked to complete a five-point self-reported scale, rating their experience as “Inferior,” “Somewhat inferior,” “Same,” “Somewhat superior,” or “Superior” compared to their first impression trial.

The independent variable assessed in this study was the method of gag control (standard distraction, temporal tapping, or acupressure), while the dependent variables were gag reflex severity measured using the GPI and subjective patient comfort as recorded on the response scale. Data were entered into Microsoft Excel (v2010) and analyzed using the Statistical Package for Social Sciences (SPSS v21.0, IBM, USA). Parametric data such as age were compared using Student’s *t*-test, and gender distribution was compared using the Chi-square test. Intragroup and intergroup comparisons of ordinal gag scores (GPI) were performed using Friedman’s test and Mann–Whitney U test respectively, while differences in frequencies of responses on the five-point scale were analyzed using the Chi-square test. For all statistical analyses, a *p*-value <0.05 was considered statistically significant.

III.RESULTS

Thirty patients were randomly allocated equally into three groups: Group 1 (Standard Distraction), Group 2 (Temporal Tapping), and Group 3 (Acupressure). Baseline demographics including age and gender showed no statistically significant differences across groups ($p > 0.05$).

The gag reflex was objectively assessed using the Gag Prevention Index (GPI) at 0 seconds, 30 seconds, 1 minute, and 2 minutes after impression tray placement. Mean GPI scores for each group are presented in Table III . Group 3 (Acupressure) demonstrated the lowest gag reflex severity throughout all time points with mean scores of 0.8, 1.0, 0.9, and 0.9 respectively. Group 2 (Temporal Tapping) had intermediate control with scores of 1.4, 1.7, 1.2, and 1.1, while Group 1 (Standard Distraction) showed the highest gag intensity with scores of 3.3, 3.5, 3.6, and 3.8 respectively.

Statistical analysis using the Mann–Whitney U test showed significant differences between Groups 3 and 1 and between Groups 2 and 1 at all time points ($p < 0.01$). Additionally, Group 3 showed statistically superior control compared to Group 2 at the 0 and 30-second intervals ($p < 0.05$). No significant differences were noted between Groups 2 and 3 at 1 and 2 minutes ($p > 0.05$).

Patient comfort was evaluated through a 5-point patient reported scale after the second impression. Table IV displays the distribution of patient-reported experiences. Group 3 recorded the highest mean comfort score (4.6 ± 0.4), followed by Group 2 (3.2 ± 0.6), and Group 1 (1.4 ± 0.5). Chi-square analysis revealed significant differences between Group 3 and Group 1 ($p < 0.001$) and between Group 2 and Group 1 ($p = 0.022$). Differences between Groups 2 and 3 were significant only at a trend level ($p = 0.061$).

TABLE III
MEAN GAG PREVENTION INDEX (GPI) SCORES OVER TIME

Time Point	Standard Distraction (Group 1) Mean \pm SD	Temporal Tapping (Group 2) Mean \pm SD	Acupressure (Group 3) Mean \pm SD
0 seconds	3.3 \pm 0.6	1.4 \pm 0.5	0.8 \pm 0.3
30 seconds	3.5 \pm 0.5	1.7 \pm 0.6	1.0 \pm 0.4
1 minute	3.6 \pm 0.5	1.2 \pm 0.4	0.9 \pm 0.3
2 minutes	3.8 \pm 0.6	1.1 \pm 0.3	0.9 \pm 0.3

TABLE IV
PROPORTIONS IN 5-POINT PATIENT REPORTED SCALE

Score	5-point patient reported scale	Group 1: Standard Distraction	Group 2: Temporal Tapping	Group 3: Acupressure
5	Superior experience	1	3	7
4	Somewhat superior experience	1	3	4
3	Same experience	2	5	3
2	Somewhat inferior experience	4	2	1
1	Inferior experience	7	0	0
	Proportions showing same or superior experience	4/15 (26.7%)	11/15 (73.3%)	14/15 (93.3%)
	p value (vs Standard Distraction)		0.022*	<0.001*

IV. DISCUSSION

Managing an exaggerated gag reflex non-pharmacologically involves multiple approaches that include simple behavioral distraction, desensitization strategies, and adjunctive methods such as salt application on the tongue, prosthetic training devices, acupuncture, transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation (TENS), and laser stimulation [8,9]. The standard distraction method involves redirecting the patient's cognitive focus through verbal communication, breathing techniques, or other distractions. Although easy to apply and well known, it primarily addresses the psychological aspect of gagging without directly influencing the neurological reflex pathways. Its effectiveness is more limited, especially in severe cases where somatic triggers predominate [16].

Temporal tapping uses rhythmic mechanical stimulation along the temporal-sphenoidal line to modify sensory input and reduce hypersensitive reflex arcs. Originating from applied kinesiology, this technique interrupts involuntary reflex pathways, offering moderate gag reflex suppression. However, because it acts indirectly via sensory distraction rather than targeting central neurophysiological mechanisms, its effect may be less robust and less consistent than acupressure [17].

Acupressure is a non-invasive technique which is easy to perform, and low risk. In acupressure, firm pressure is applied to sensitive points on the body called "caves" or 'Suan-Zhang' to alleviate symptoms such as pain, nausea, and gagging. Important points for gag reflex control include Neiguan (P6)—located on the anterior wrist about three finger breadths from the wrist crease, Hegu (LI4)—in the hollow between thumb and forefinger, and Chengjiang (CV24)—midway between lower lip and chin. Among these, Neiguan (P6) exerts the most direct effect on the gag reflex by modulating autonomic nervous system activity through sensory afferent fibers that stimulate the central release of neurotransmitters like serotonin and β -endorphins, which inhibit nausea and gag reflex pathways. This neurophysiological mechanism leads to more consistent reflex suppression and better patient tolerance. In the present study, Neiguan (P6) point was preferred over Hegu and Chengjiang points due to its well-established clinical efficacy, ease of access for pressure application, and safety profile in dental contexts. While Hegu primarily influences pain and anxiety, and Chengjiang is mostly for orofacial symptoms, the direct autonomic modulation at P6 explains its superior effectiveness and practicality [10,19].

Patients in our study preferred acupressure due to its consistent and noticeable reduction in gag reflex intensity and enhanced comfort during procedures. Unlike temporal tapping, which involves repetitive mechanical action that some may find distracting or uncomfortable, and standard distraction that requires constant cognitive engagement, acupressure offers a continuous, gentle pressure that many find soothing and effective. This likely contributes to higher patient satisfaction and acceptance of acupressure as a gag reflex management tool [10,17].

Overall, while all three methods have roles in gag reflex management, acupressure stands out for its neurophysiological mechanism, ease of application, and patient preference. Still, employing standard distraction techniques alongside sensory-based methods optimizes outcomes by addressing both psychological and physiological components of gagging.

Limitations include a modest sample size and lack of blinding inherent to manual behavioural interventions. Future studies could explore synergistic effects of combining acupressure with other non-pharmacological modalities such as low-level laser therapy or transcutaneous electrical nerve stimulation to further enhance gag reflex control.

V. CONCLUSION

In conclusion, this study demonstrates that non-pharmacological methods, including standard distraction, temporal tapping, and acupressure, can effectively manage increased gag reflex during dental treatments. Acupressure, especially at the Neiguan (P6) point, showed superior efficacy through direct modulation of autonomic pathways that suppress gag reflex and nausea, resulting in greater patient comfort. Temporal tapping, which provides mechanical sensory stimulation, showed moderate benefit by altering sensory input. The standard distraction method mainly relies on cognitive diversion and displayed limited effectiveness alone.

Patient preference favoured acupressure because of its continuous, gentle pressure, ease of application, and rapid relief, compared to the variable effects of temporal tapping and cognitive demands of distraction. Combining sensory-based techniques with distraction may further improve gag reflex control by addressing both physiological and psychological aspects. Future studies with larger samples and incorporating adjunct approaches like low-level laser therapy could provide enhanced gag reflex management strategies in dental practice.

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CONFLICT OF INTEREST

The authors declare that they have no conflicts of interest.

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Figure 1
Standard Distraction Method

Figure 2
Temporal Tapping technique

Figure 3
Acupressure at Neiguan (P6) Point